

Human Resource Management As Correlate Of Teachers' Recruitment Process, Teachers' Welfare And Instructional Delivery In Primary Schools In Gusau Education Zone Of Zamfara State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the relationship between human resource management as correlate of teachers' recruitment process. Teachers' welfare and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone of Zamfara state, Nigeria. The study has two specific objectives and two null hypotheses. The study adopted the correlational survey research design. A sample size of 200 was purposively selected to represent the population of 2,001. Also, the multi-stage sampling technique was used to select the respondents. Two instruments that included; Human Resource Management Scale (HRMS), and the other adapted version of Teacher Instructional Delivery Observation Checklist (TIDOCL) were used for data collection. The two instruments were validated by the experts in educational research, test and measurement in education from the Faculty of Education and Extension Services, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. The reliability of the two instruments was determined through a trial test in five primary schools that were not included in the main sample for the study. The test re-test method was applied and the data obtained was subjected to Cronbach alpha analysis, yielding a reliability value of 0.81 and 0.87. The data analysis was done using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) with application of the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The findings revealed among others, that there was a significant positive relationship between teachers' staff welfare (motivation) and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau educational zone of Zamfara state, Nigeria. Consequently, the study recommended among other things that government should as matter of urgency improve teachers' welfare through provision of incentives and regular payment of certain allowances such as leave grants to primary school teachers in the state.

Keywords: Human resource, Instructional delivery, Management, Primary School.

INTRODUCTION

Primary education in Nigeria plays a pivotal role in the development of the country, as it lays the foundation for lifelong learning, personal development, and the acquisition of essential literacy and numeracy skills. According to United Nation Educational Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) (2016) primary education is critical in building cognitive skills that foster a child's ability to

learn effectively in subsequent educational levels and promotes social, emotional, and intellectual development.

Human Resource Management as it relates to teaching and learning is measured through teachers' recruitment and welfare (motivation), while instructional delivery refers to effective teaching and learning outcomes. The literature review highlights studies on HRM practices influence on instructional delivery. Human Resource Management (HRM) refers to the processes of planning, recruiting, developing, motivating, and retaining employees to achieve institutional goals (Sharma & Pandey, 2021). In the educational context, HRM integrates both teaching and non-teaching staff to enhance productivity and ensure quality instruction. Effective HRM promotes creativity, skill development, and teacher loyalty, while poor HRM results in low morale, absenteeism, and poor instructional outcomes (Dlamini, Du Plessis & Markham, 2023). Also, Akpakwu in Adejumo (2018), stresses that transparent and merit-based recruitment enhances teacher performance and school effectiveness.

Teacher recruitment involves attracting and selecting qualified individuals to fill teaching positions. In Nigeria, political interference and non-merit-based recruitment often undermine educational quality (Ibiene, & Eberechi, 2024). Recruitment based on competence and subject specialization ensures that schools employ teachers capable of meeting curriculum demands. Merit-based recruitment practices improve instructional delivery by ensuring that well-qualified teachers are employed, thereby enhancing teacher-pupil interaction, instructional quality, and overall academic performance.

Teachers' welfare includes financial and non-financial benefits such as salaries, allowances, housing, promotions, and recognition. Adequate welfare contributes to job satisfaction, motivation, and retention (Esie, 2023). Motivation, whether intrinsic (personal satisfaction) or extrinsic (financial rewards), drives teachers to perform effectively (Ibiene & Eberechi, 2024). Poor welfare policies lead to low productivity, frequent absenteeism, and teacher attrition, which negatively affect instructional delivery (Ugochukwu, Adaobi & Anyaeji, 2021). Conversely, fair compensation, timely payment, and professional recognition improve teacher morale and performance. Motivation remains a key factor for promoting effective classroom instruction and sustaining teacher commitment to educational goals.

Instructional delivery refers to the methods and strategies used by teachers to effectively convey curriculum content. Hornby (2015) defines instruction as the implementation phase of the curriculum. With this, it can be seen that instructional delivery encompasses all activities that facilitate learning and behavioral change. Effective instructional delivery depends on the teacher's planning, teaching methods, use of materials, and learner engagement (Napocao, 2016). Teachers who are well-trained and motivated are more likely to use learner-centered and interactive approaches, leading to improved comprehension and performance among pupils.

Instructional delivery at the primary education level involves the use of culturally relevant teaching materials and approaches, which can help foster a sense of identity and social cohesion among pupils. It is pertinent to note that in contexts where instructional materials reflect the learners' cultural backgrounds and experiences, learners are more likely to engage with the content, ultimately improving learning outcomes. In contrast, instructional delivery that does not consider learners' socio-cultural contexts, may lead to loss of interest or disengagement, undermining educational effectiveness. Effective instructional delivery requires adequate, relevant and good management system of educational resources. Effectiveness of management is highly dependent on the availability of human resource in particular.

Quality primary education is seen as instrumental in reducing poverty, enhancing social equity, and supporting economic development, given that it prepares children to participate effectively in the society and contributes to a skilled workforce in the country. Achieving high-quality primary education depends significantly on effective human resource management and instructional delivery. As such, Instructional delivery, which encompasses the methods and strategies teachers use to engage learners in learning (Adejumo, 2025). Instructional delivery in Nigerian primary schools is especially important because of the wide disparities in educational access and quality across regions and socioeconomic groups. Effective instructional delivery, characterized by active teaching methods, structured curriculum content, and

learner-centered learning, positively impacts pupils' engagement and learning outcomes (Olayinka & Oladejo, 2019).

Existing literature have shown that there is poor human resource management in almost all sectors of education in Nigeria and this appeared to have contributed to the declining standard of education in almost every state (Zamfara inclusive), especially at primary school level. Gladys, Nicholas and Crispen (2016) noted that many pupils do not perform to their expectations due to the faulty human resource management practice as the consequence of which is seen in quality of teachers' recruitment process and staff welfare (motivation) as well as performance management. These vital areas of human resource management are not properly implemented by those in charge of education administration and this has led to underperformance on the part of teachers; many report late to work, leave early, attend irregularly, get alternative work elsewhere and even engage in regular strike actions as a way of resenting poor treatment from the school management and the government as well. This in turn lead to poor learning achievements among pupils.

Despite the existing studies on both HRM and instructional delivery, there remains a gap in understanding the direct relationship between HRM and instructional delivery. Many existing studies on human resource management, devoted attention mostly on HRM as a discipline. Limited works existed on relationship between HRM and other aspects of academic discourse bordering on teachers or learners related variables. Therefore, the current study focused on investigating the relationship between human resource management and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau educational zone of Zamfara State, Nigeria. By identifying and addressing the existing gap, the study aims to provide practical recommendations for policymakers, educational administrators, and teacher development programs to foster a more efficient and impactful education system. In view of this, human resource management seems to be the most crucial factor in the provision of quality education (because all other resources are subject to human manipulation at the school level). It is based on this backdrop that the present study was carried out.

This study is anchored on the System Theory proposed by Von Bertalanffy (1972), which views organizations as systems made up of interdependent parts working together toward a common goal. In the educational context, HRM represents the input, instructional delivery represents the process, and learning outcomes represent the output, while supervision and evaluation provide feedback. Effective HRM strengthens the instructional process and enhances overall educational performance, demonstrating how systemic interaction among components promotes efficiency and quality (Garba, 2018).

Similarly, in the work of Mwirigi and Muthaa (2015) who found that teacher shortages in Kenyan primary schools led to overworked teachers and reduced instructional quality. In study of Suleiman (2016) who reported that inadequate staffing and poor personnel management hindered Universal Basic Education implementation in Nigeria. In another place Dlamini *et al.* (2023) observed that recruitment and retention challenges negatively affected teacher performance in rural Eswatini schools. In the study of Ibiene and Eberechi (2024) who discovered that teacher training and motivation significantly enhanced instructional delivery in Port Harcourt primary schools. Also, in another place, Ezeaku (2019) found that improved welfare and funding strengthened teacher commitment in Anambra State. In the work of Rabi (2017) who reported that poor facilities, irregular payment of salaries, and inadequate staff development reduced instructional effectiveness in Sokoto State.

The reviewed studies consistently show that teacher recruitment and welfare are crucial determinants of instructional quality. However, few studies have directly examined their combined influence on instructional delivery at the primary education level in Gusau education zone of Zamfara State, Nigeria with an empirical gap this study seeks to address.

Statement of the Problem

In Nigeria, huge human resource has been invested in the education sector, and covering all level of schooling. However, the quality of teachers in primary schools has not really matched up with the investment at that level. Some of the problems bedeviling the public primary schools in relation to human

resource management might be connected with poor quality performance appraisal, training, and orientation of newly employed teachers. This situation has led to decline in the quality of teachers in the primary schools and impede their instructional performance. Many teachers at the primary school level lacked the proficiency to effectively deliver instructions needed in the 21st century classroom (Elenwo & Oteyi, 2024). For instance, the researcher observed that Gusau education zone of Zamfara state primary education system is facing a lot of challenges in the management of human resource for achieving quality instructional delivery in primary schools in the education zone in particular and the state in general.

Also, the researcher (being a stakeholder in primary education) observed that there are issues bordering on quality of teachers' recruitment process and staff welfare. It is obvious that, the failure on the authorities concerned with primary education to address these challenges has led to poor learning environment; low education quality and increase in dropout rates. Equally, poor instructional delivery negatively impacted on learners' ability to engage meaningfully with curriculum content. Therefore, addressing the issues of human resource management is essential for creating a more equitable and effective educational system that can support all learners at primary education level to realize their potentials.

Based on the researcher's review of available literature, there are a lot of issues and challenges that posed a wide gap in the allocation, availability, adequacy and management of human resource. Also, researches carried out in Gusau education zone of Zamfara state with regards to the prevailing issues and challenges, in primary schools appeared to be very scarce. Hence, parents in Gusau education zone of Zamfara state and other stakeholders in primary education, are not certain whether primary education is likely to meet the desired objectives due to the above problems and challenges. Therefore, the current study was carried out to examine the relationship between human resource management and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone of Zamfara state.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are as follows;

1. To find out if there is any relationship between quality of teachers' recruitment process and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone.
2. To find out if there is any relationship between status of teachers' welfare and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested to guide the study:

Ho1. There is no significant relationship between quality of teachers' recruitment process and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone.

Ho2. There is no significant relationship between staff welfare (motivation) status and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone.

METHODOLOGY

The design of the study was correlational survey design and the population comprises of 2001 teachers in the 459 primary schools located within the three (3) Local Government Areas in Gusau education zone. Using multi stage sampling procedure, the researcher has in the first stage deliberately selected three local government areas out of the four LGAs that constituted Gusau education zone, The selected LGAs included Gusau, Bungudu and Maru. However, Tsafe was excluded due to security challenges. Also, in the second stage, a total of 46 public primary schools were selected based on proportionate sampling and covered in the study. Equally, in the third stage, a total of 200 teachers was drawn from the selected schools using proportionate sampling technique and used as the sample size for this study. Two instruments were used for data collection in this study. The first one was designed by the researcher and titled "Human Resource Management Scale (HRMS). The second instrument was tagged 'Teacher Instructional Delivery Observation Checklist (TIDOCL)' and it was an adapted version of the Faculty of Education and Extension Services Students' Teaching Practice (TP) Assessment Report Form. The first

instrument (HRMS) was subjected to face validation by 3 experts who are specialist in Test and Measurement, Educational Management and Primary Education respectively, from the Faculty of Education and Extension Services, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto. While the second instrument (TIDOCL) was an adapted version of the Faculty of Education and Extension Services student Teaching Practice (TP) assessment report form and was subjected to revalidation by three experts who are members of the teaching practice committee. A reliability testing was carried out using 30 classroom teachers from the school which were not part of the main sample of the study. The Cronbach's Alpha was used and a coefficient value of 0.81 was obtained, which indicated that the instruments (HRMS) and (TIDOCL) are reliable.

Results

Testing Null Hypotheses

The null hypotheses formulated in this study were tested and the results were presented at a 0.05 level of significance using PPMC as follows:

Ho1: There is no significant relationship between quality of teachers' recruitment process and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone of Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Table 1: Relationship between quality of teachers' recruitment process and instructional delivery

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	r-Cal	p-value	Decision
Recruitment Process	200	15.196	6.498	198	.040	.030	Rejected
Instructional Delivery	200	68.742	6.556				

Source; Fieldwork, 2025.

From Table 1, it can be seen that the relationship between quality of teachers' recruitment process and teachers' instructional delivery is positive and significant, r-Cal = .040, p-value (.030) is less than 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis that says there is no significant relationship between quality of teachers' recruitment process and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone of Zamfara State, Nigeria is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between the quality of teachers' recruitment process and teachers' instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone of Zamfara State, Nigeria. This means that the better the quality of teachers' recruitment process the better the instructional delivery by teachers.

Ho2. There is no significant relationship between staff welfare (motivation) status and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone of Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Relationship between staff welfare and instructional delivery

Variable	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	r-Cal	p-value	Decision
Staff Welfare	200	14.085	6.971	198	.059	.032	Rejected
Instructional Delivery	200	68.742	6.556				

Source; Fieldwork, 2025.

From Table 2, it can be seen that the relationship between staff welfare and teachers' instructional delivery is positive and significant, r-Cal = .059, p-value (.032) is less than 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis that says there is no significant relationship between staff welfare (motivation) status and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone of Zamfara State, Nigeria is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between staff welfare (motivation) status and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone of Zamfara State, Nigeria. This means that the better the teachers' welfare provision, the better the instructional delivery by teachers. By implication, it can be deduced that teachers' welfare is an instrument to better instructional delivery.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first finding of this study as reflected in Table 1 shows the hypothesis tested on relationship between quality of teachers' recruitment process and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone of Zamfara state, Nigeria. From the statistical analysis provided in the table, it is clearly indicated that the relationship between quality of teachers' recruitment process and teachers' instructional delivery is positive and significant, $r=0.040$, $p=0.030$ which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis that says there is no significant relationship between quality of teachers' recruitment process and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone of Zamfara state, Nigeria is here by rejected. By implication, there is significant relationship between quality of teachers' recruitment process and instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone of Zamfara state, Nigeria. The finding of the study supports the work of Semako (2019) in which it was revealed that there is significant relationship between teachers' academic qualification and students' academic performance in the classroom teaching and learning situation. Meaning that, if teachers with the required academic qualifications were recruited certainly the students/learner's academic performance will be greatly enhanced. This finding of the study equally confirmed the work of Ibiene and Eberechi (2024) reports that recruitment of teachers into schools should be done based on requirement and area of needs. Thus, this will not only improve teaching but will also help improve the quality of education in the education zone in particular and the state in general. Conclusively, it is important to note that, the better the quality of teachers' recruitment process the better the instructional delivery in the schools.

The second finding of this as reflected in Table 2 indicates the hypothesis tested on relationship between teachers' welfare (motivation) and instructional delivery in primary schools in Zamfara state, Nigeria. From the statistical analysis provided in the table, it is clearly shows that the relationship between teachers' welfare (motivation) and teachers' instructional delivery is positive and significant, $r=0.059$, $p=0.032$ which is less than 0.05 level of significance. As such, the null hypothesis that says there is no significant relationship between teachers' welfare (motivation) and teachers' instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone of Zamfara state, Nigeria is here by rejected. Impliedly, there is significant relationship between teachers' staff welfare (motivation) and teachers' instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone of Zamfara state, Nigeria. The finding of the study concurs with the work of Lemos, Muralidharan and Scur (2022) in which they reported that improving funding to education sector and better welfare package for teachers are needed for effective management of public schools. Meaning that, to ensure effective and efficient operation of public schools with a view to achieving the stated educational goals and objectives, improvement of funding to the sector as well as provision of better welfare package for teachers are of paramount necessity. Equally, the finding agreed with the work of Agah and Yakubu (2024) reveals that fringe benefits and staff development have significant impact on teachers' job performance.

On the other hand, this finding of the study contradicted the work of Manga (2020) where he reveals that the level of teacher productivity was rated low; professional status and condition of service which involved teachers' welfare (motivation) were both rated poor. Thus, this unfavourable situation has negatively influenced teacher productivity. The finding equally disagreed with the work of Ibi, Gwary, and Adamu (2020) to some extent reveals that there was no significant relationship between pay-package and teachers' productivity, no significant relationship between working environment and teachers' productivity, no significant relationship between implementation of promotion and teachers' productivity and there was no significant relationship between job security and teachers' productivity. However, it agreed with their work in this alternative hypothesis where they stated that there was a significant relationship between fringe benefits and teachers' productivity. In conclusion, it is pertinent to note that, the better the teachers' welfare provision the better the instructional delivery by the teachers.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that better teachers' recruitment process and better teachers' welfare (in terms of good payment of salary and allowances) are essential in promoting teachers' instructional delivery in primary schools in Gusau education zone of Zamfara state, Nigeria. From the findings of the study, there was a clear manifestation of the fact that teachers are motivated through regular payment of salaries, recognition of the dedicated and hardworking teachers by both education zone, SUBEB and school authorities in the state. However, there is a clear area of concern regarding replacement of existing vacancies as well as allowances as most teachers assert that they are unmotivated in terms of regular payment of allowances. This has been observed from the responses of 200 respondents on the twenty (20) item statements which were premises of the two (2) research questions raised and two (2) null hypotheses formulated earlier in this study.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. There is need for the government to do everything possible to ensure quality recruitment process at all the time and equally enforce the due process and avoid replacement on the existing vacancies. It is important to note that only when better quality recruitment process is adopted that better instructional delivery can be realized from the teachers.
2. Since it was discovered that in Gusau education zone of Zamfara state, there is regular salary payments and various forms of recognition from both authorities and PTA contribute positively to teachers' welfare, there is need for the government to ensure provision and regular payment of allowances so as to boost the morale of teachers and improve their welfare status.

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